
Rethinking Antimicrobial Innovation: A Policy Blueprint for Sustainable Discovery and Development Incentives

Executive Summary

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is outpacing today's innovation model. We recommend two pillars to reset the pipeline with a public-health lens:

1. Strengthen early-stage science and bridge the preclinical-to-clinical gap, and
2. Deploy equitable pull incentives that reward success without widening access inequalities.

We frame both pillars in a One Health, data-driven approach that uses modern AI—specifically foundation models (e.g., large language models) and multimodal learning—to integrate signals across human, animal, and environmental domains. We recommend two immediate priorities:

1. Europe must invest in early science and bridge the preclinical-to-clinical gap.
2. Europe must design pull incentives tied to equitable access.

To succeed, these tools must be embedded in a One Health framework and supported by modern AI. Foundation-model AI (large language models and multimodal systems) can accelerate discovery and trial design—but only if fed with curated, high-quality data from human, veterinary, and environmental sources.

Key actions for the EU Presidency and Commission:

- Establishing a coordinated EU-wide funding framework that combines targeted push and pull tools, leveraging distributed expertise rather than a centralised facility.
- Scaling public funding via Horizon Europe, IHI, and a dedicated AMR instrument.
- Building on models like CARB-X and the AMR Action Fund, public R&D funding in Europe should be explicitly centered on One Health based antimicrobial stewardship plans.
- Expanding civil society's role in education, accountability, and uptake.
- Advance advocacy through targeted stakeholder coalitions, including civil society, academic networks, and patients' organizations, to shape legislative implementation and ensure incentive models remain aligned with public health outcomes
- Embed technical guardrails in all stages of policy development for AMR R&D

This package gives Europe an actionable way to lead globally: clear investment signals, practical incentives, and accountable equity safeguards.

1. Introduction

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a major threat to global health. Despite growing awareness and stewardship, novel antibiotic development has stalled. Most approved candidates offer only marginal improvements, leaving resistance pathways unaddressed. Promising targets like quorum-sensing inhibitors and synthetic molecules remain stuck in early research due to fragmented funding and weak incentives, including the absence of post-approval pull mechanisms (1).

Policy efforts have focused on late-stage rewards like Transferable Exclusivity Vouchers (TEVs), which offer market benefits but don't address upstream challenges such as underfunded labs or the discovery-to-validation gap (2,3). Scientific leaders advocate shifting investment toward foundational science to enable novel, resistance-breaking treatments (4–6). Several civil society actors promote accountability and responsible use, urging a move away from commercialization toward early-stage discovery (7).

In April 2024, the European Parliament revised pharmaceutical legislation to prioritize AMR and integrate a One Health approach (8). This framework provides an opportunity to align innovation with public health objectives. The current pharmaceutical reform process builds on a decade of fragmented incentive proposals in Europe, from early discussions of TEVs to emerging subscription pilots. Yet, without coordination and technical guardrails to regulate AI outputs, funding mechanisms like Horizon Europe and the EU Commission Health Emergency Preparedness and Response Authority (HERA) risk inefficiency.

This paper proposes a strategy built on early discovery, equitable access, and a tiered incentive system. While grounded in EU policymaking, it is globally adaptable.

2. Rebuilding the Discovery Pipeline

The stagnation in antibiotic discovery stems from a dual failure: underfunded early science and a lack of scalable development incentives. Unlike oncology, which has benefited from decades of investment, antimicrobial research and development (R&D) suffers from inconsistent support and a loss of talent (9-11).

To reignite discovery, innovation must focus on:

- Novel drug targets beyond classical pathways (e.g., quorum sensing).
- Overcoming Gram-negative permeability barriers through rational compound design.
- Natural product revival using genome mining and synthetic biology, with safeguards to preserve microbial biodiversity and ensure sustainable sourcing in line with One Health — further complicated by the access and benefit-sharing requirements of the Nagoya Protocol.

- Integrating AI, omics, and high-throughput screening tools in balanced, evidence-based ways.
- Pathogen-agnostic strategies (e.g., immunity footprint) and cross-disease research linking bacterial exposure to cancers and autoimmune conditions (12).

Efforts should extend to antifungal innovation, given the rise of multidrug-resistant fungi like *Candida auris*. This broadening aligns with the One Health approach and amplifies the significance of AMR research.

While some funding exists, it remains sporadic, inadequately scaled and mainly linked to basic research and AMR monitoring. A hybrid financing model is needed: predictable public grants, structured private-sector engagement, and performance-linked support. Targeted push funding, particularly for the transition from preclinical to early clinical development, is critical to prevent promising candidates from failing in this high-risk phase (6,13).

EU-level coordination through Horizon Europe, the Innovative Health Initiative (IHI), and a dedicated AMR fund would ensure consistency, amplify resources, and set a model for international collaboration.

3. Incentive Models for Sustainable Innovation

TEVs have dominated AMR policy discussions in Europe but remain untested. These incentives offer exclusivity extensions for other products. Unless structured carefully to focus TEVs on products with clear novelty or utility, they could inflate costs without improving access or stimulating innovation (2,14).

Importantly, TEVs (and indeed, any incentive model) would need to provide substantial value to be able to address the critical bottlenecks in early-stage discovery and the transition into clinical development. Economic modeling suggests that meaningful incentives for a new antibiotic must reach between €2.9 and €4.3 billion, far beyond what TEVs in Europe alone can deliver (15).

Effective AMR innovation requires an incentive portfolio aligned with the R&D lifecycle. We propose three categories aligned across the push (including targeted clinical transition funding) and pull continuum, with One Health and equity safeguards embedded throughout (Figure 1):

Figure 1. Multi-Layered Incentive Framework for Sustainable Antimicrobial Innovation

Figure 1. Multi-Layered Incentive Framework for Sustainable Antimicrobial Innovation

This figure maps the alignment of incentive mechanisms across the antimicrobial R&D timeline, from discovery through market entry. **Push funding** supports early-stage research, including grants, public–private partnerships, and foundational science initiatives. **Targeted push funding** bridges the high-risk preclinical-to-clinical transition, ensuring promising candidates are not lost due to capital gaps. **Pull incentives**, such as subscription models, revenue guarantees, and other delinkage-based approaches, reward successful products post-approval while safeguarding equitable access. Cross-cutting layers of One Health integration and equity safeguards are embedded through multi-sectoral influence and impact considerations into the discovery process and span all stages, ensuring that scientific advances translate into global public health benefits.

A. Pull-Incentive Fund and Subscription Models

Global pull incentives are impractical. Instead, coordinated international reimbursement schemes should be linked to shared common principles for innovation and equitable distribution (16). Pull incentives should reward success post-approval. Pre-approval "mini-prizes" should be avoided due to manipulation risks.

Subscription models, like the UK's, guarantee annual payments for approved products, are an example of a way to decouple revenue from sales volume. These agreements should include performance metrics such as guaranteed stockpile delivery.

Well-designed revenue guarantees tied to access conditions can serve as powerful pull mechanisms. They should be sized appropriately and implemented with transparency (2).

In addition, delinking sales from revenue helps prevent over-marketing and supports access. Subscription models create predictable markets, enabling developers to invest in supply stability and registration in diverse settings (17).

These models ensure availability for WHO bacterial priority pathogens (according to 2024 list,) support smaller markets, and create sustainable returns without perverse incentives.

B. Public–Private Partnerships (PPPs)

PPPs such as the Combating Antibiotic-Resistant Bacteria Biopharmaceutical Accelerator (CARB-X) for early-stage research and the Global Antibiotic Research and Development Partnership (GARDP) for late-stage development are central to sustaining the antibiotic pipeline. The CARB-X platform offers valuable lessons for structuring incentives.

As a particular opportunity in the early space, significant investment is needed in the preclinical-to-clinical transition. To fill this gap, ideas such as the following should be pursued:

- New grants should support high-risk discovery in neglected microbial niches.
- Cross-disciplinary research into how microbes contribute to chronic diseases may uncover novel therapeutic targets and expand the clinical relevance of antimicrobial discovery (18,19).

C. Sustained, Performance-Tied Push Funding

Rather than prize-based funding, R&D funding should be tied to progress validated by clear criteria. Examples include demonstrating a novel mechanism of action or progressing to Phase II with robust evidence.

Such funding mechanisms should support compound advancement and transferable methods, prioritize strategic discovery gaps, including permeability, efflux, and synergy, and avoid arbitrary timelines by tying support to verifiable outputs. No single model will solve AMR's market failures. A diversified mix of push and pull mechanisms is required, implemented in a coordinated and transparent manner (13).

4. Challenges to an Effective AMR Response

A. Challenges in AMR Science

a. Overcoming Permeability Barriers

Gram-negative bacteria pose unique challenges due to their outer membranes, requiring rational design for penetration, synthetic optimization for intracellular action, and environmentally degradable profiles (20). Gram-positive bacteria are equally problematic but remain comparatively understudied, warranting greater research investment.

B. Expanding Fungal Innovation

Fungal pathogens are rising in importance, particularly in immunocompromised patients. Similar challenges, such as penetration and toxicity, require tailored R&D support. AMR policy should explicitly include antifungal pipelines.

B. Aligning Global Priorities

- a.** While not a direct discovery barrier, fragmented research prioritization and uncoordinated funding streams continue to limit the global impact of AMR innovation. Tools like the WHO Priority Pathogens List should be updated regularly and directly linked to public and philanthropic funding incentives to sharpen focus and guide investment toward urgent threats (21–23).

International alignment is progressing through efforts like the EU’s HERA, the Global AMR R&D Hub, and the G7. These should converge into structured funding partnerships with clear governance, measurable outputs, and regional flexibility (25). For example, under Canada’s G7 leadership, a 2025 high-level AMR roundtable in Ottawa emphasized pull incentives linked to equitable access and delinkage-based reimbursement schemes (23).

Regional adaptation is equally critical. In many low-income countries, AMR innovation is impeded by weak clinical trial infrastructure, procurement bottlenecks, and limited regulatory coordination. A 2023 WHO-AFRO meeting highlighted the need for targeted support, including regulatory capacity, local manufacturing, and networked trial platforms (24). These examples illustrate how EU-driven incentive models can serve as adaptable templates, tailored to diverse national and regional contexts.

Licensing agreements must reflect this diversity, including explicit access clauses for LMICs. Civil society organizations should play a central role in monitoring implementation and ensuring accountability for equitable distribution and uptake (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Institutional Ecosystem Supporting Antimicrobial R&D in the EU and Globally

Figure 2. Institutional Ecosystem Supporting Antimicrobial R&D in the EU and Globally

This figure illustrates the multi-actor landscape supporting antimicrobial discovery and development across the R&D continuum, structured into four sequential stages. **Early-stage discovery (Push)** includes Horizon Europe, CARB-X, National Research Councils, and Academia/SMEs, which fund or conduct foundational research. **Targeted push funding coordination** involves actors such as the Innovative Health Initiative, WHO R&D Blueprint, and philanthropic organisations (e.g., Wellcome) that provide strategic resources to advance promising candidates through high-risk preclinical and early clinical phases. **Incentivised development** is supported by HERA, GARDP, and EMA, which coordinate late-stage development, regulatory guidance, and preparedness. **Post-approval pull and access** mechanisms are shaped by national payers, EU joint procurement initiatives, and civil society/LMIC access platforms to ensure equitable uptake. Visualising this ecosystem highlights the need for aligned advocacy, governance, and funding to optimise push, targeted push, and pull incentives for sustainable antimicrobial innovation.

5. Policy Implications: A Call for EU Leadership

The EU's pharmaceutical reforms recognize AMR as a priority, but financial incentives remain narrow. Proposals like the TEV must be supplemented by scalable, coordinated frameworks.

We recommend:

- Establishing a coordinated EU-wide funding framework that combines targeted push and pull tools, leveraging distributed expertise rather than a centralised facility.
 - *Justification:* Increased **Push & Pull Mechanisms** are necessary to reimagine the R&D system in place. Through enhanced **Push Mechanisms** the research through to clinical phases will be consistently supported through staged funding disbursements, allowing for regulated and consistent development milestones to be upheld. **Pull incentives** ensure stability in the clinic to market transition through transitions away from prize-based awards, supporting more equitable market entry and developer assurance, incentivising further investment and development.
- Scaling public funding via Horizon Europe, IHI, and a dedicated AMR instrument.
 - *Justification:* In support of expanded **Push Mechanisms**, increased investment in One Health based public funding models allows for increased access R&D. A dedicated AMR instrument prioritizes funding incentives to counter research investment and interest to previously better funded sectors, such as oncology or bariatrics.
- Building on models like CARB-X and the AMR Action Fund as an example of a dedicated AMR instrument, public R&D **Push funding** in Europe should be explicitly centered on One Health based antimicrobial stewardship plans (ASPs).
 - *Justification:* One Health approaches are necessary to anticipate the cross-sectoral reality of disease emergence and response. This approach is necessary in combination with ASPs to bring forward a globally interlinked action plan against AMR.
- Expanding civil society's role in education, accountability, and uptake.
 - *Justification:* Including public capacity and increasing awareness must be included to create a One Health approach in AMR R&D. Increased public awareness is also an important part of post-market ASPs to factor in public adherence to antibiotic stewardship protocols, like decreasing the occurrence of “leftover” antibiotics and antibiotic sharing.
- Advance advocacy through targeted stakeholder coalitions, including civil society, academic networks, and patients' organizations
 - *Justification:* Coalitions between the core groups involved in varying stages of R&D is key to making sure diverse voices are included in legislative implementation and ensuring **pull incentive** models remain aligned with public health outcome.
- Explore a network of public biomedical innovation actors:
 - *Justification:* In organizations like the Centre national de la recherche scientifique (CNRS) in France or the Helmholtz Association of German Research Centres, researchers coordinate their work across sites and disciplines. Building on these examples, *public biomedical innovation actors* should be expanded to avoid inefficiencies of centralised facilities by

leveraging a distributed network of existing groups (25). It could directly address neglected science, manage IP for affordability and access, and align innovation with public health needs. Stakeholder consultation should determine whether it acts as a funder, R&D performer, or hybrid.

- Embed technical guardrails in all stages of policy development for AMR R&D
 - *Justification:* Due to AI's advanced processing capacity, A One Health AI approach to R&D presents an opportunity to demonstrably enhance discovery (discovery from multimodal data, pattern recognition, compound optimisation, integration of computational biologists into discovery teams) considered alongside other tools such as omics and high-throughput screening. However, without sufficient regulation of accurate inputs and outputs AI inclusions risk a 'garbage in- garbage out' approach. Guardrails including LLM constraint models like NVIDIA's NeMo and human screening requirements for AI outputs are necessary to ensure accuracy and ethicality of AI inclusion.

6. Conclusion

AMR innovation must shift from reactive, post-market fixes to proactive, science-driven strategies. The EU has the momentum, infrastructure, and influence to lead. By investing in early-stage research, targeting funding to high-risk transitions, deploying fit-for-purpose **push & pull incentives**, and embedding equity safeguards, Europe can set a new global standard for antimicrobial innovation.

References

1. Miethke M, Pieroni M, Weber T, Brönstrup M, Hammann P, Halby L, et al. Towards the sustainable discovery and development of new antibiotics. *Nat Rev Chem*. 2021;5(10):726–49.
2. Outterson K, Powers JH, Daniel GW, McClellan MB. Repairing the broken market for antibiotic innovation. *Health Aff (Millwood)*. 2015;34(2):277–85.
3. Anderson M, Towse A, Outterson K, Mossialos E. Implementing an EU pull incentive for antimicrobial innovation and access: blueprint for action. *Lancet Microbe*. 2024;5(10):100886.
4. Lewis K. The science of antibiotic discovery. *Cell*. 2020;181(1):29–45.
5. Piddock LJ. Antibiotic resistance: challenges and opportunities. *Nat Rev Microbiol*. 2012;10(3):211–8.
6. Walsh TR. A One Health framework for tackling antimicrobial resistance. *Nat Rev Microbiol*. 2020;18(7):428–9.
7. ReAct-Europe, European Public Health Alliance. Position paper on EU incentives for new antibiotics development. 2022 Jul [cited 2025 Feb 26]. Available from: <https://epha.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/antibiotic-incentives-pharma-legislation-joint-paper-2022.pdf>

8. Amand-Eeckhout L. Revision of EU pharmaceutical legislation. European Parliamentary Research Service; 2024. Report No.: PE 749.789.
9. Silver LL. Challenges of antibacterial discovery. *Clin Microbiol Rev.* 2011;24(1):71–109.
10. Theuretzbacher U, Outterson K, Engel A, Karlén A. The global preclinical antibacterial pipeline. *Nat Rev Microbiol.* 2020;18(5):275–85.
11. Högberg LD, Heddini A, Cars O. The global need for effective antibiotics: challenges and recent advances. *Trends Pharmacol Sci.* 2010;31(11):509–15.
12. Morand A, Cornu M, Drouin AC, Couvelard A, Naudin J, Desnues B. Human microbiome and carcinogenesis: a systematic review. *Ann Biol Clin (Paris).* 2020;78(6):577–88. doi:10.1016/j.biopha.2020.110280. (Original source referenced: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0165247820300377>)
13. Årdal C, Baraldi E, Ciabuschi F, Outterson K, Rex JH, Piddock LJ, et al. The market dynamics of antibiotics: creating incentives for innovation. *Nat Rev Drug Discov.* 2020;19(12):725–6.
14. O'Neill J. Tackling drug-resistant infections globally: final report and recommendations. London: Review on Antimicrobial Resistance; 2016. Available from: https://amr-review.org/sites/default/files/160518_Final%20paper_with%20cover.pdf
15. Zong Z, Walsh TR, Venter H, Keating D, Li X, Toleman MA. The impact of antibiotic discovery and development on AMR. *J Antimicrob Chemother.* 2019;74(7):1875–7.
16. Renwick MJ, Simpkin V, Mossialos E. A global financing strategy for sustainable antibiotic innovation. *Lancet Infect Dis.* 2016;16(11):1380–2.
17. Schneider M, Daniel GW, Harrison NR, McClellan MB. Delinking US antibiotic payments through a subscription model in Medicare. Duke-Margolis Center for Health Policy; 2020.
18. Alm RA, Gallant K. Innovation in antimicrobial resistance: the CARB-X perspective. *ACS Infect Dis.* 2020;6(6):1317–22.
19. Calore M, Fraundorfer M. The One Health framework and its implementation in global health governance through public-private partnerships. University of Leeds; 2020.
20. Tamma PD, Cosgrove SE, Maragakis LL. Combination therapy for treatment of infections with gram-negative bacteria. *Clin Microbiol Rev.* 2012;25(3):450–70.
21. Tacconelli E, Carrara E, Savoldi A, Harbarth S, Mendelson M, Monnet DL, et al. Discovery, research, and development of new antibiotics: the WHO priority list of antibiotic-resistant bacteria and tuberculosis. *Lancet Infect Dis.* 2018;18(3):318–27.
22. World Health Organization. Global priority list of antibiotic-resistant bacteria to guide research, discovery, and development of new antibiotics. Geneva: WHO; 2017.
23. Global AMR R&D Hub, World Health Organization. Incentivising the development of new antibacterial treatments: G7 progress report. 2024 Oct.
24. WHO Regional Office for Africa. Meeting Report: Advancing AMR Innovation and Access in Africa. Brazzaville: WHO AFRO; 2023.
25. Biomedical innovation in Berlin gets €30 million boost [Internet]. Mdc-berlin.de. 2025 [cited 2025 Sep 19]. Available from:

<https://www.mdc-berlin.de/news/press/biomedical-innovation-berlin-gets-eu30-million-boost>

Working group members:

- ❖ *Rodrigo Scotini*, Executive Director, IDA
- ❖ *Carl Aryan*, Partnership & Committees Director, IDA
- ❖ *Paraskevi Saridaki*, Science Associate, IDA
- ❖ *Tine Rikke Jorgensen*, WHO EURO Consultant
- ❖ *Kim Lewis*, Professor, Director of Antimicrobial Discovery Center, Northeastern University
- ❖ *Enkelejda Miho*, Professor at the University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland FHNW
- ❖ *Mélanie Raimundo Maia*, Assistant Professor in Global Digital Health, WHO Collaborating Centre on Health Workforce Policy and Planning, Global Health and Tropical Medicine, Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Portugal
- ❖ *Michael Schloter*, Director of the Research Unit for Comparative Microbiome Analysis, Helmholtz Munich
- ❖ Mohamed Sirdar, Global Program Specialist (AMR), International Society for Infectious Diseases (ISID)

The authors thank John H. Rex, MD (Editor-in-Chief, AMR.Solutions), David McKinney (Co-Founder & Director, ARMoR), and Jens Jäger (Delegate for the research field Health, Brussels Office of the Helmholtz Association of German Research Centres) for constructive comments on the paper.

Disclaimer: personal views, not representing institutions...